

Common Infrastructure for National Cohorts in Europe, Canada, and Africa - CINECA -

Deliverable D5.3 - GDPR and FAIR compliant Diagnostic Services

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1. Executive Summary

Within this deliverable the results of subtasks 5.3.1 (*Analytical sandbox for diagnostic services*) and 5.3.3 (*GDPR/FAIR compliant Diagnostic reporting*) are described. D5.3 demonstrates tying together the technical ideas and research developed in CINECA into accessible, end-user applications - removing the need to have deep technical understanding of the various components. In this case the tools are applied to identifying pathological - and thus clinically-relevant - variants.

The general context of D5.3 can be seen in Figure 1 as the final steps in the application of the CINECA tools where the relevant datasets have been discovered and combined using CINECA federated tools to generate a larger variant database to drive more accurate conclusions. Additionally, variant databases could be created and validated that are more tuned to diagnostics in non-caucasian populations that have historically been under-represented in reference data - a problem that tools such as those developed in CINECA/GA4GH would hope to reduce in future.

In the specific case of D5.3 this would mean changing the training data using these larger datasets obtained by federated search (e.g. WP1-3) to derive more representative conclusions (the upper-highlighted section in Figure 1). Current day-to-day application of the system would be most suitable for research purposes. Diagnostic use would be possible if the correct legal framework depending on country and region would be in place and relevant well-validated, stable reference data is present. (For example) EGA¹ datasets that have been identified using the WP1-3 tools in the 5.3.1 Analytical Sandbox could in principle be used as reference datasets.

Figure 1 - ST5.3.1 and ST5.3.3 in context

¹ <https://ega-archive.org/>

However, subtask (ST) 5.3.1 does support interfacing directly to resources such as the EGA if this manner of usage of the analytical pipeline is required.

To this end D5.3 provides:

- An “analytical sandbox” - essentially an algorithm deployment and execution environment that is largely pre configured from a technical/scientific parameter perspective so that it can be locally installed with relatively basic technical skill.
- A FAIR-compliant data upload, storage, analysis and reporting system aimed at simplifying annotation of a patient’s data with variant pathogenicity information as a model for a simplified genetic report that might be used to inform a clinician as to the most relevant variants.

The analytical sandbox is provided by Subtask (ST) 5.3.1 and was set up with a direct connection to the European Genome-phenome Archive (EGA), enabling researchers to remotely log in to perform analysis from anywhere in the world. Within the analytical sandbox a workflow was deployed to process next-generation sequencing (NGS) data, starting from sequenced reads in FASTQ format and resulting in a list of prioritised variants that could explain a patient's phenotype, as such providing the infrastructure and bringing genomic data analysis to researchers or diagnosticians without access to HPC compute facilities.

The FAIR-compliant reporting demonstrator (ST5.3.3) is the Diagnostic Reporting Application (DRA), a system designed to generate diagnostic reports based on genomic SNP variants. It aligns with GDPR/FAIR principles, which ensure data privacy/usage safeguards and make data “Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable”. The DRA integrates a variety of deliverables from other work packages, such as the VIP pipeline (WP ST5.3.1) and a customised instance of the Molgenis EMX2 “Fair Data Hub” (WP T5.2). The DRA generates diagnostic reports by extracting likely pathogenic variants from the VIP output and presenting them alongside variant-associated disease information from Disgenet. The system stores data according to FAIR principles and has undergone a FAIR Maturity Assessment, resulting in good scores in the Findable and Interoperable aspects, with Accessible and Reusable aspects being largely compliant. The use of FAIR data principles may have limited utility in the context of clinical patient applications where privacy is paramount, but the system can be useful within an organisation or consortium intranet where data access and patient consent can be realistically arranged with suitable security precautions.

At the heart of D5.3 are various algorithms and tools - of which the main one is CAPICE [18] that has been developed at UMCG within CINECA² with the aim of identifying known *pathological* variants that are thus likely to be more clinically-relevant as opposed to purely of interest to academic researchers.

² Superseding the GAVIN algorithm referred to in the original CINECA proposal.

2. Project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has demonstrated practical application of the technologies developed within CINECA by non-expert users via

- A preconfigured “sandbox” analytical service - in this case focused on the area of rare diseases, but which could equally be applied to other conditions.
- A reporting solution (using the above service as one data source) that provides processes input in a FAIR-compliant manner providing access to the data, reports and associated metadata for the purposes of discovering and reproducing the process.

3. Detailed report on the deliverable

3.1 Analytical sandbox for diagnostic services (Subtask 5.3.1)

3.1.1 Background

Subtask 5.3.1 can be separated into two parts, first the cloud infrastructure (the sandbox), and second the analysis pipeline (the diagnostic services), together enabling an analytical environment. In this report firstly the sandbox will be described as implemented in CINECA, based upon the Solve-RD analysis cloud. Functionalities on the connection between the sandbox and the EGA, developed within the CINECA project and also utilised within Solve-RD³ and EJP-RD⁴ are described separately.

Analytical Sandbox

The analytical sandbox is a high-performance computing (HPC) environment aimed at bioinformaticians to enable analysis of genomic NGS data using open-source pipelines to provide variant calling and prioritisation for those without a local compute facility. Such an HPC environment consists of multiple computers linked together by a single scheduler and having a large storage (many Terabytes). This enables researchers and diagnosticians to perform analyses that are not possible on a desktop. The environment is a CINECA specific group of the Gearshift HPC cluster, physically located in Groningen, The Netherlands. The CINECA group has shared storage and computing with other groups and projects. However, the CINECA group is accessible only to approved CINECA-affiliated people. The cloud environment is aimed at bioinformaticians because it uses a Linux operating system to be controlled using a command-line interface. The analytical sandbox allows for federated analysis by connecting to the EGA archive, providing the option to utilise data drawing on the cumulative services from WP 1,2 and 3.

An overview diagram of the diagnostic services within the analytical sandbox can be seen in Figure 2 . Essentially, the sandbox architecture allows for portable, easy-to-configure execution of the scientific “analysis” modules contained in the grey blocks.

³ <https://solve-rd.eu/>

⁴ <https://www.ejprarediseases.org/>

A

B

Figure 2 - Diagnostics services (A) pipeline description and (B) workflow diagnostics services within analytical sandbox

The cloud environment has been designed for interoperability and reproducibility and is therefore developed in close collaboration with similar activities in other projects, in particular European Joint Programme for Rare Diseases (EJP-RD) WP11.4, EXCELERATE, CORBEL, SolveRD and EOSC-Life. It has been designed to be fully reproducible, meaning that it can be completely installed on a different cloud provider in exactly the same configuration such that outputs of analysis pipelines are exactly the same.

3.1.2. Description of Work

Analytical Sandbox

1. A virtual computer cluster. This layer provides the storage space and cpu's, and is based on industry standard OpenStack[1]. The pilot CINECA diagnostic cloud environment is hosted at the Center of Information technology from the University of Groningen. Using this approach we have converted our compute cluster into virtual machines (VMs) that can be installed on clouds using the

OpenStack software. The CINECA diagnostic cloud is part of an instance of what is internally known as ‘league of robots’⁵.

2. The operation system and HPC configuration layer. The cluster uses a Linux operating system and provides a way to log in, currently using a double-hop access, through a security hardened jumphost (called “airlock”) to the cluster (called “gearshift”). Gearshift therefore is an internal network, not directly connected to the internet, creating a secure environment. Sign-on to the diagnostic cloud is done using a private and public key pair. These digital keys can be easily created by users. The user should add a password to the private key, that can then be used to encrypt data (close the lock). The private key should not be shared by the users and stored safely in their local environment. The associated public key can be shared and can be used to decrypt data. The cloud host can store the public key in IDVault (where cloud access is managed) to enable the user to enter the diagnostic cloud. For additional background and details see Wikipedia – Public Key Cryptography [2].

The CINECA group storage is split into two parts, a temporary (tmp) and a permanent (prm) storage folder. Data stored in the tmp folder can be used for analysis, but is not backed up. Results from finished analyses or raw data that should be kept safe in the sandbox can be stored in the prm folder, which is backed up.

3. The ‘slurm’ software is used to allow for execution of many analyses in parallel on the cluster. Slurm then automatically distributes the work over the compute nodes allowing for the most efficient use of available resources and manages book-keeping of analyses performed. Currently available tools can be found here: <https://github.com/molgenis/easybuild-easyconfigs/tree/master/easybuild/easyconfigs>

4. The bioinformatics software configuration. Reference data and analysis tools are provided through a toolchain, based on Easybuild. Using a module system tools (or specific versions of them) can be easily loaded and upon creation of a new cloud instance the same toolchain can be easily deployed. Analysis workflows can be managed using the MOLGENIS/compute workflow framework in which Linux-based compute workflows can be created and executed with logging. Using the slurm ‘sinfo’ command the available nodes can be seen. On the gearshift cloud this looks like the screenshot in Figure 3.

```

GEARSHIFT
=====
Welcome to Gearshift
=====
WARNING: only prm* group dirs are backedup.
When this cluster has to be redeployed from scratch,
all data in home dirs and tmp* & rsc* group dirs will be lost!
=====
Fetching available environment modules from /apps/modules/... s done!
[umcg-ljohansson@gearshift ~]$ sinfo
PARTITION    AVAIL  TIMELIMIT  NODES  STATE NODELIST
regular*     up 7-00:01:00    2  drain gs-vcompute[04,06]
regular*     up 7-00:01:00    8  mix gs-vcompute[01-03,05,07-10]
user_interface up 7-00:01:00    1  idle gearshift

```

Figure 3: Screenshot of the info results on the gearshift HPC cluster.

⁵ The complete ‘cookbook’ for installing the cloud foundation is at <https://github.com/rug-cit-hpc/league-of-robots>

Within this pilot the Linux based cloud can be accessed through a command line interface. For MacIntosh the 'terminal' can be used to log in, once the public and private key pair and configuration have been set correctly. On a Windows machine a Linux emulator, such as Cygwin[3] or MobaXterm[4] could be used. The latter has next to a command-line view also a point-and-click procedure to copy files to and from the cloud. This enables non-bioinformaticians to get access to the cloud and stage raw data for analysis or retrieve analysis results. While the commandline is the way of working for the diagnostic cloud, other options to access the cloud are possible to share data. For instance an SFTP server can be connected to the cloud to enable easier up- and download of data. For more documentation see <http://docs.gcc.rug.nl/gearshift/index.html>.

Dataset

Within the subtask two datasets located at the European Genome-Phenome Archive (EGA) were used:

1. The GoNL dataset, produced within the Genome of the Netherlands consortium and includes sequence data from 767 individuals from 250 families. Sequencing is performed as whole genome sequencing at an average coverage of 12x. Sequencing has been performed on an Illumina HiSeq2000 system. The raw data (FASTQ) files are included in EGA dataset: <https://ega-archive.org/datasets/EGAD00001000821>
2. RD-Connect B1MG synthetic rare disease dataset. This dataset contains fastq files, BAM files and gVCF files as well as phenopackets and PED files. The dataset can be accessed on <https://ega-archive.org/datasets/EGAD00001008392>.

Both datasets contain for each case two parents and a child (or two).

EGA fuse-client and download-client

To enable access to data located outside the analytical sandbox, a connection with the European Genome-Phenome Archive (EGA) has been set up [5].

Two ways of accessing data within the EGA archive, given permission, are incorporated in the analytical sandbox. Direct access through the ega-fuse-client⁶ and indirect access through the pyEGA3 download client, based on the GA4GH htsgit protocol⁷. During the project several iterations of these clients were installed, including a beta-test of the download client. Access to the EGA datasets through the ega-fuse client using Ansible protocol⁸.

In the sandbox within the Cineca group an ega-fuse-client folder is present in the prm folder. Within this folder, based on the EGAD a folder was created, giving direct access to the files within the dataset.

⁶ <https://github.com/EGA-archive/ega-fuse-client>

⁷ <https://github.com/EGA-archive/ega-download-client>

⁸ https://github.com/rug-cit-hpc/league-of-robots/tree/develop/roles/ega_fuse_client (internal repository UMCG/CIT)

Diagnostic services

Within the diagnostic cloud project a two-part pipeline was implemented. Both pipelines have been developed in the context of the EJP-RD project [6] and are used here as a use-case. The first part of the pipeline starts with an NGS raw sequence file, in FASTQ format[7], then aligns the sequence reads to a reference genome and determines on which locations the patient's DNA sequence differs from the reference. This leads to a series of variant calls. Within this project the focus is on single nucleotide variants (SNVs) and small insertions or deletions (indels) up to 50 base-pairs. The called variants are stored in a VCF file format[8]. The tools have been combined to a pipeline using the MOLGENIS/compute workflow language[9]. Within our pipeline we make use of bwa-mem[10] and GATK4[11][12] for alignment and variant calling.

The second part of the double-pipeline configuration consists of the MOLGENIS Variant Interpretation Pipeline (VIP)[13][14], of which version 4.5.1 was used for the use-case analysis. Here the VCF file is used as input as well as phenotypic information of the patient that can be passed into the pipeline using Human Phenotype Ontology (HPO). In addition, pedigree information can be used by VIP to perform inheritance matching. Finally, BAM files can be added as an input. These do not have a function in variant classification, but for each variant in the report a slice of the bam file is included that can be used as a source of information on the support of sequence reads for this variant call.

VIP is a flexible system to prioritise the genetic variants provided in the VCF on the likelihood to be causal for a patient's phenotype. VIPs main added value is that it is modular and configurable, integrating best in class software, such as ENSEMBL Variant Effect Predictor[15], SpliceAI[16], gnomAD[17] or CAPICE[18]. Validated decision protocols are designed from routine diagnostics practice and inputs from the CINECA project as well as from the EJP-RD and Solve-RD projects help further improve protocols. VIP provides annotation, prioritisation and filtering of variants from which users can create custom filter trees to classify variants. Moreover, interactive HTML reports can be generated to filter and select variants of interest, e.g based on the quality of the call, phenotype matching or inheritance matching. Filtered VCF files can be exported from the HTML file, based upon current filter settings. Examples of the HTML file and the VCF exports can be seen in the results section in Figures 4 and 5.

Within the analytical sandbox next to the other tools available in the toolchain two pipelines are available that together can process next-generation sequencing (NGS) data, the GATK4 pipeline and VIP. In between those pipelines currently a preprocessing step is necessary to create a combined VCF file for the parents and the child (a trio), to be able to determine if a variant is *de novo* or not.

The demonstration analysis is meant to show a workflow for diagnostics bioinformaticians without local access to HPC computing. Here, we demonstrate a workflow in which data submitted to and archived by the EGA can be accessed and analysed from within the diagnostic cloud. Below the workflow of running the GATK4 pipeline is described.

File staging and verification

1. Firstly, the dataset, located at the EGA, as described in the Methods section, needs to be accessed. This can be done using a credentials file, using credentials provided by the EGA. Using the pyEGA3 download client, fastq files were copied to the analytical sandbox. Alternatively, fastq

files were accessed directly through the ega fuse client. pyEGA3 analysis was performed using the RD-Connect B1MG synthetic rare disease and ega fuse client analysis was performed using a sample from the GoNL dataset.

2. The checksums of the copied files are calculated
3. The checksums of the files at the EGA are retrieved.
4. The checksums of the copied files are compared to those of the original files.

GATK4 pipeline: read alignment and variant calling

Then the NGS-GATK4 pipeline was started. Protocol and samplesheets are described on https://molgenis.gitbooks.io/ngs_dna/content/ and https://molgenis.gitbooks.io/ngs_dna/content/ngs-samplesheets.html

5. In the tmp directory of the main group (here umcg-cineca), six folders are created, which the pipeline expects to exist: 'generatedscripts', 'logs', 'projects', 'rawdata' (with subfolder 'ngs'), 'Samplesheets' and 'tmp'.
6. In the Samplesheet directory a samplesheet can be created that needs to be called PROJECT_NAME.csv. The samplesheet should have (at least) the following 19 columns to pass the relevant subject, sample, experiment and file metadata to the pipeline:

externalFastQ_2: PE read 2 fastq.gz

arrayFile: Leave empty if no array is present for concordance check

lane: Fill in the lane on which the sample was sequenced

externalFastQ_1: : PE read 1 fastq.gz

run: Fill in run1 if this is the first time you are analyzing this sample with the pipeline (otherwise run2 etc.)

sequencingStartDate: Fill in the date at which was sequenced

Gender: Fill in Male, Female or Unknown

MotherSampleId: Fill in ID of mother if known, this could enable a trio analysis

barcode: Fill in the sequencing barcode of this sample e.g. TCTTCACA-CAGTCGTG or CAGTCGTG or None (e.g. from name fastq file or from within fastq file)

project: Fill in the project name (should be the same as the project folder name that you will create later

capturingKit: Fill in the capturing kit here. It should match a folder in /apps/data. In case of whole genome sequencing use UMCG\wgs. If the capturing kit

is not present it should be created based on a bed file. Contact `hpc.helpdesk AT umcg dot nl` for this.

`flowcell`: Fill in flowcell ID (e.g. from name fastq file)

`hpoIDs`: Fill in HPO terms if known

`sequencer`: Fill in sequencer ID if known (e.g. from name fastq file)

`externalSampleID`: Fill in the name of the sample (e.g. Sample1)

`seqType`: Fill in the sequencing type (e.g. PE or SR)

`FatherSampleId`: Fill in ID of father if known, this could enable a trio analysis

`FatherAffected`: Fill in if the father is affected or not (Yes or No)

`MotherAffected`: Fill in if the mother is affected or not (Yes or No)

`FirstPriority`: Leave on FALSE in normal cases, if one sample should be processed first put on TRUE.

7. Within the `tmp` directory a `PROJECT_NAME` folder needs to be created and the `samplesheet` needs to be copied here.
8. Within the `generated_scripts` directory a `PROJECT_NAME` folder needs to be created
9. The NGS pipeline module needs to be loaded
10. There is a generate template script that needs to be copied to the folder created in step 8. The script has to be set to work with external samples.
11. In addition the `samplesheet` needs to be copied to the same folder.
12. Now the generate template script from step 10 can be run. A `scripts` folder will be created with a submit script. The jobs to run the pipeline will be generated upon running the submit script.
13. The jobs can be submitted to the SLURM scheduler using a newly created submit script.

The output of the first part of the pipeline as described by steps 1 to 13 are binary sequence alignment map (BAM) files, containing aligned sequence reads, and genomic Variant Call Format (gVCF) files, containing the called genetic variants as well as information on the quality of the variants and the reference base calls. For each chromosome a separate gVCF file is created.

The second part of the analysis is performed using a second pipeline, the MOLGENIS Variant Interpretation Pipeline (VIP). For the pilot analysis VIP 4.5.0 was used. This version of VIP supports VCF as input format. This means that the gVCF files have to be preprocessed before being used as input for VIP. If the analysis is performed with multiple family members, these can be preprocessed together. This creates a single VCF file for all family members containing all positions on which at least

one has a variant. This allows reference calls to be distinguished from variant positions in which no good base call could be made.

File preprocessing for VIP

Preprocessing is performed in two steps. Firstly all chromosome gVCF files from all family members to be analysed are combined into a single gVCF file. This step is performed by the combineGVCFs function of the Genome Analysis Tool Kit (GATK), version 3.8.1.0. And secondly a genotype caller is used on this file to transform the gVCF file into a VCF file containing the base calls for all family members of positions where at least one of them has an alternative base call. This step is performed by the same tool kit using the GenotypeGVCFs function.

VIP

VIP version 4.5.0 was used for analysis⁹. This version can be started using an Easybuild module. Note that later versions (VIP v5 and higher) are started differently.

A configuration file can be created to override default settings on memory and cpu usage and allowed time per step.

The main inputs of VIP are

1. The combined VCF file as created during the preprocessing steps
2. The Human Phenotype Ontology (HPO) terms of the patient phenotypes
3. The pedigree (PED) files describing the relations between the family members.
4. Optionally BAM files can be used as input for VIP.

3.1.3 Results

VIP results B1MG RDConnect synthetic dataset

For the three analysed samples from the B1MG RDConnect synthetic dataset reports were generated, starting from FASTQ (Figure 2), resulting via alignment, variant calling and variant interpretation. For each case the final output was the VIP report, an interactive HTML report, (Figures 2, 4 and 6) with optional download of VCF file (Figure 6). In the figures the result of **Case 2** is given as an example. Via a secure copy the report can be copied to your local computer and opened in a web browser.

⁹ <https://github.com/molgenis/vip/releases/tag/v4.5.0>

VCF Report Samples Variants

Home / Samples / P0007501 / Variants

Sort by: CAPICE (descending)

3 records

HPO	Position	Reference	P0007501	P0007503	P0007502	Effect	Gene	Inh.Pat.	HPO	HGVS C	HGVS P	CAPICE	VIP	VKGL	ClinVar var...	gnomAD AF	gnomAD HN	PubMed
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> HP0000529	4:16037357	C	G/T	G/T	C/C	splice_donor_variant	PROM1	AD	AR	HP0000575, HP0007703	c.303+1G>A	0.952	LP		P_LP	0.0000	0	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> HP0000575	11:6638385	C	G/T	G/T	C/C	splice_acceptor_variant	TFPI1	AR		HP0000529	c.509:1G>A	0.9712	LP	LP	P	0.0000	0	citations (9)
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> HP0007703	15:28114774	G	G/A	G/A	G/G	intron_variant	OCA2	AD	AR	HP0007703	c.2244+1526C>T	0.0045	LP			0.0109	3	

Filters: HPO (checked), VKGL (checked), ClinVar.variant (checked), P0007501 (checked), Inheritance (checked), Read depth >= 20 (checked).

Figure 4: resulting interactive HTML report showing causal variant **PROM1** as highest prioritized of three variants filtered from ~3 million variants.

```

##fileformat=VCFv4.2
##FILTER=ID=PASS,Description="All filters passed"
##ALT=ID=NM_REF,Description="Represents any possible alternative allele at this location"
##CAPICE_CL=CAPICE classification
##CAPICE_SC=CAPICE score
##FILTER=ID=LowQual,Description="Low quality"
##FORMAT=ID=AF,Number=A,Type=Integer,Description="Allelic depths for the ref and alt alleles in the order listed"
##INFO=ID=AC,Number=A,Type=Integer,Description="Allele count in genotypes, for each ALT allele, in the same order as listed"
##INFO=ID=AF,Number=A,Type=Float,Description="Allele Frequency, for each ALT allele, in the same order as listed"
##...
##InheritanceModesGene=List of inheritance modes for the gene
##SpliceAI_pred_DP_AD=SpliceAI predicted effect on splicing. Delta position for acceptor gain
##...
##VEP=^v105^ time="2022-08-09 09:10:51" cache="/groups/umcg-cineca/tmp01/VIP/vip/resources/vep/cache/homo_sapiens_refseq/105_GRCh37" ensembl-variation=105.acb17e ensembl-funogen=105.660df8f ensembl=105.525fbc ensembl-io=105.2ab
##VIP=VIP decision tree classification
##VIP_Command=nextflow -config /groups/umcg-cineca/tmp01/VIP/cineca_diagnostic_cloud_BIM2_Cases123/scripts/vip_config_gearshift_wgs run /groups/umcg-cineca/tmp01/VIP/vip/main.nf -resume -profile cluster --assembly GRCh37 --input
##VIP_Version=4.5.1
##VIP_TreeCommand=nextflow -input FMM0001815_chunk0_annotated.vcf.gz --config /groups/umcg-cineca/tmp01/VIP/vip/resources/decision_tree.json --output FMM0001815_chunk0_classified.vcf.gz
##VIP_TreeVersion=3.2.3
##VKGL_CL=VKGL consensus variant classification.
##contig=ID=1,length=24920621,assembly=b37
##...
##reference=file:///app/data/10000/phase1/human_g1k_v37_ph1K.fasta
##source=haplotypecaller
##...
#CHROM POS ID REF ALT QUAL FILTER INFO FORMAT P0007501 P0007502 P0007503
4 16037357 . C T 179.16 AC=2;AF=0.333;AN=6;BaseRankSum=-2.019;CQ=T;splice_donor_variant|HIGH|PROM1|8842|Transcript|NM_006017.3|protein_coding||4/27|NM_006017.3|333c.303+1G>A|||||||rs77673930|||||1|1|EntrezGene||
11 6638385 . C T 1746.16 AC=2;AF=0.333;AN=6;BaseRankSum=-1.214;CQ=T;splice_acceptor_variant|HIGH|TFPI1|1200|Transcript|NM_000391.4|protein_coding||15/12|NM_000391.4|333c.509-1G>A|||||||rs561441254|CS971463|CS9913444|COSY5-4|
15 28114774 . G A 1694.16 AC=2;AF=0.333;AN=6;BaseRankSum=-2.235;CQ=A;intron_variant|MODIFIER|OCA2|4948|Transcript|NM_000275.3|protein_coding||21/23|NM_000275.3|333c.2244+1526C>T|||||||rs727105591|||||1|1|1|EntrezGene||
    
```

Figure 5: VCF download of the interactive HTML report listing prioritized variant **PROM1** as first of three variants filtered from ~3 million variants.

Figure 6: expanded interactive HTML report showing molecular pathogenic variants that do not need to match inheritance patterns (e.g. single variant in a gene connected to a recessive disease). Four variants are highlighted: low quality (C), and not matching inheritance, next to originally shown variants (A, B, D). Variants are sorted on CAPICE score (decreasing).

In all three test cases from the RD-Connect B1MG synthetic rare disease dataset the spiked causal variant or variants were part of the list of variants in the final selection, ranging from 3 to 11 remaining candidate variants (Table 1).

Case	Disease	Pattern	VIP rank causal variant / total number of variants to assess
Case 1	Congenital myasthenic syndrome	Autosomal Dominant De Novo	4/11
Case 2	Macular dystrophy	Autosomal Dominant	1/3
Case 3	Muscular dystrophy	Autosomal Recessive Compound Heterozygous	2/8 and 4/8

Table 1: VIP rank of causal variant(s) in the RD-Connect B1MG synthetic rare disease dataset.

3.1.4 Next steps

The Molgenis Variant Interpretation Pipeline (VIP) has regular releases¹⁰ and is now being expanded to include FASTQ, BAM and gVCF files as input formats, thereby allowing VIP to be the sole pipeline used for analysis, easing analysis.

3.2 GDPR/FAIR Compliant Diagnostic Reporting (Subtask 5.3.3)

3.2.1 Background

The Diagnostic Reporting Application (DRA) is a demonstrator of a diagnostic reporting system that provides a wrapper around a genetic diagnostic analysis pipeline highlighting SNP variations with known pathology associations.

The DRA has been designed to align with GDPR/FAIR principles, which provide guidelines for data privacy/usage safeguards and making data “Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable”, respectively. The FAIR aspects of the DRA are discussed in more detail later in the document and Appendix 1. In addition, the DRA integrates or has used some deliverables from other work packages, such as WP ST5.3.1 (described earlier in this document) and WP T5.2 (see D5.2 and <https://github.com/molgenis/molgenis-emx2>).

The original CINECA proposal from 2018 had intended to contribute to the “MolDia” project with potential direct application to live patient data necessitating a strict audit of GDPR issues. This project has been discontinued and thus does not form part of this deliverable. However, the DRA still protects the privacy and traceability of data to conform to the GDPR but has only been applied to publicly-available datasets. Additionally, for a demonstrator only anonymized data are loaded on the assumption that in a real-world clinical situation any directly patient-identifying data would be held elsewhere and linked to the DRA data in a separate system.

3.2.2 Description of Work

Overview of the DRA

The DRA is designed to generate a report based on medical data collected from patients at the level of genomic SNP variants. The application generates a diagnostic report that provides clinicians with information about key SNP variations that are known to have pathological implications - see Figure 7.

¹⁰ <https://github.com/molgenis/vip/releases>

Figure 7 - DRA Overview

The important stages of the analysis (raw analysis input and output data, individual variant results and the report) are stored in a manner following FAIR principles [19] to ensure that these artefacts are **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable, and **R**eusable – notably by the use of controlled vocabularies and ontologies to support “computer-friendly” interrogation of available resources.

Implementation of the DRA

In the implementation process, we first incorporated an instance of the VIP pipeline, which converts VCF files into prioritised variants. This pipeline is a part of the analytical sandbox for diagnostic services in WP ST5.3.1 and is described earlier in this document.

The VIP pipeline as used in the DRA was chosen for:

- A. Its clinically-relevant calling of pathogenic variants based on the UMCG CAPICE algorithm [20] – an updated replacement for the GAVIN (Gene-Aware Variant INTERpretation for medical sequencing) algorithm [21].
- B. Scalability as the underlying Nextflow engine has good support for future execution in HPC environments and is used elsewhere in CINECA so some expertise was available.

The second component implemented was another CINECA-supported application – a customised instance of the Molgenis EMX2 “Fair Data Hub”, which is part of WP T5.2. Molgenis offers customizable data schemas to support FAIR data and is thus a preferable long-term sustainable solution.

The third component was the DRA, developed as an R Shiny application that generates a diagnostic report based on the VIP variant calling output. The report is created by extracting pathogenic and likely pathogenic variants from the VIP output, and for each variant, incorporating variant-associated disease information identified from Disgenet¹¹ into the report. An example report is given in the Appendix 2 of the document and a view of the user interface is given below in Figure 8:

¹¹ <https://www.disgenet.org/home/>

POSITION	VARIANT	GENE	DISEASE	CLASS
1:976215-976215	rs7417106	PERM1	NA	NA
1:979034-979034	rs536503119	PERM1	NA	NA
1:52904685-52904685	rs72670819	ECHDC2	NA	NA
1:74205390-74205390	rs55882158	FPOT	NA	NA
1:88983825-88983825	NA	RBMXL1	NA	NA
1:89054646-89054646	NA	GBP1	NA	NA
1:226735904-226735904	rs708776	ITPKB	NA	NA
1:249441258-249441258	NA	OR2T7	NA	NA
2:86110465-86110465	rs72645618	SMYD1	NA	NA
3:42915240-42915240	NA	ZNF602	NA	NA
3:91448378-91448378	NA	LOC101930420	NA	NA
3:128153626-128153626	rs76829052	EEFSEC	NA	NA
3:169122674-169122674	rs34896995	MCCOM	NA	NA

Figure 8 - R Shiny User Interface of the DRA

An overview of the system is given in Figure 9 below and the three components interact in the following manner:

1. DRA controls the VIP pipeline, allowing users to upload a VCF file to the analysis and to execute the process.
2. DRA uploads the VIP output to Molgenis to ensure compliance with the FAIR principles.
3. DRA generates the diagnostic report and submits it to Molgenis.
4. DRA registers the relevant data files with an external Persistent Identifier (“PID”) service provided by GRNET¹² (part of the EU ePIC project¹³) to present a maintained, computer-searchable resource to allow access to the data in the long-term.

Figure 9 - DRA Pipeline

¹² <https://epic.grnet.gr/>

¹³ <http://www.pidconsortium.net/>

Registration of Persistent Identifiers

PIDs are useful as long-term, maintained registry entries for artifacts (documents, data, etc.) that are typically invariant for a given artifact, but where the underlying URL to access the data can be updated by the originator to preserve external accessibility and avoid problems such as “reference rot”¹⁴. To promote continuity in this area the EU ePIC consortium maintains such registries and we have used the GRNET registry in the demonstrator (links referred to in the previous paragraph).

The artifacts that are registered as part of the DRA process are:

1. Input data file (VCF)
2. Output data file (Annotated VCF)
3. Report file (HTML/PDF)

Additionally, PID links to the relevant metadata (e.g. data creation, datatype, etc.) for these artifacts are registered.

For example, the direct access URL for the report file for Patient “P1234” might be accessible from the DRA at a locally URL that is implementation-dependent and could change due to local policy, IT restructuring, etc:

`http://cgocineca.uk:8080/CFAIR/api/file/PathReport/fileData/5a47afd7e24a44718752c5576bd1e584`

However, registering this at the PID service will make this URL accessible from a *permanent* PID handle/URL via the ePIC API:

`https://hdl.grnet.gr:8001/api/handles/21.T15999/b895e6e6-95e4-5d7f-a768-18b9556c8f05`

...where it is the data owner’s responsibility to maintain the appropriate local URL as the target of the permanent PID.

Note that the naming convention uses globally-unique ids (“GUIDs”) to remove any semantic meaning from the PID handle. A future implementation might register IDs via a formal paid-for DOI registration agency to mint “doi:” identifiers instead.

3.2.3 Results

Testing & FAIR Assessment

We tested the DRA using public datasets, focusing on the correct generation of reports and compliance with FAIR principles, such as searching for the generated reports and pathological variants highlighted by VIP/CAPICE.

¹⁴ see <http://hdl.handle.net/10.1371/journal.pone.0115253>

FAIR querying via RDF/SPARQL

Datasets are presented according to the Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT) RDF specification¹⁵ allowing automated querying via a SPARQL endpoint presented on the server. As a demonstration of FAIR access to the data, we conducted a search from a specific patient ID to discover the report metadata and then to download the particular report – “walking” down the various RDF triples to discover the information in a computer-friendly way - see Figure 10.

Figure 10 - Walking down RDF data from Individual to Report

FAIR Maturity Assessment

Finally, we conducted a “FAIR Maturity Assessment” [22] of the application resulting in good scores in the Findable and Interoperable aspects. The Accessible and Reusable aspects being largely compliant bar some issues relating to long-term preservation and automated access to licensing.

Long-term preservation is something that could easily be solved in a production system, however the issue of licensing was not something that was considered during the project, and in hindsight should have been addressed - even if only in a basic form, should a comprehensive licensing solution be difficult to implement given the potential different licences attached to input data in this context, From a purely technical perspective implementing concepts such as RDF licences¹⁶ (e.g.) and the “DUO” Data Use Ontology¹⁷.

¹⁵ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-2/>

¹⁶ e.g. <https://creativecommons.org/ns#License>

¹⁷ <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/duo.owl>

3.2.3 Next steps

Naturally, beyond this demonstrator it would be desirable to add a more complex data schema and more sophisticated security, naming conventions, etc. but this is out-of-scope and the essential principles can be seen in action with the DRA.

The FAIR principles are only really applied to the *data* in ST5.3.3 and to be fully reusable a FAIR description of the actual process and all subcomponents should be added - but applying FAIR principles to *processes* is not such a mature field as applying them to data so this would require active research to implement.

It should be noted that the use of FAIR data principles might only have limited utility in the context of clinical patient applications where privacy is naturally paramount – notwithstanding the fact that the DRA would only use anonymized data and identifiers. So, in practice such tools may only be useful *within* an organisation or consortium where data access, patient consent, etc. can realistically be arranged with suitable security precautions – in contrast to the typically “open” flavour that FAIR research data access has. However, it is indeed possible that in a large organisation proper computer-compatible access to data will add value for internal projects by simply improving data tracking/provenance to support future studies.

4. Overall conclusion

D5.3 is a demonstrator of practical applications of CINECA developments that have been set up to be used by technical users. The produced output reports are meant to aid genetic variant interpretation by non-technical users including clinicians and researchers.

The ST5.3.1 Analytical Sandbox allows for the execution of various complex analytical tools from any location using a computer- with examples in the area of rare diseases. It is capable of taking data from various sources, including via remote, federated datasources identifiable using other CINECA tools from WP1-3 and executing the algorithms with very little setup. Additionally, it is customizable by the addition of new pipelines that can be plugged into the sandbox framework according to the needs of the end-users. The diagnostic service (MOLGENIS VIP) generates comprehensive interactive reports for genomic specialists to interpret and is usable in both research and diagnostic settings.

In contrast, the ST5.3.3 DRA generates a simplified diagnostic report aimed at providing clinicians with information about a patient's genetic makeup in the context of pathogenic SNP variants. It is a FAIR-compliant application that integrates a variety of deliverables from other work packages, and the use of standardised data formats and controlled vocabularies and publishing as a “FAIR Data Point”¹⁸ ensures that the data used/generated in the application is “Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable”.

¹⁸ <https://www.fairdatapoint.org/>

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7. Abbreviations

BAM	Binary Alignment Map
B1MG	Beyond 1 Million Genomes Project
EGA	European Genome-Phenome Archive
DCAT	Data Catalog Vocabulary
GATK	Genome Analysis Tool Kit
GA4GH	Global Alliance for Genomics and Health
GoNL	Genome of the Netherlands
gVCF	genomic VCF
HPC	High Performance Compute
HPO	Human Phenotype Ontology
HTML	HyperText Markup Language
MOLGENIS	MOlecular GENomics Information System
NGS	Next-Generation Sequencing
RDF	Resource Description Framework
SLURM	Simple Linux Utility for Resource Management
VCF	Variant Call Format
VIP	MOLGENIS Variant Interpretation Pipeline

8. Delivery and schedule

Delivered on May 9th 2023

9. Adjustments made

The following adjustments have been made to the deliverable compared to the original CINECA proposal:

- ST5.3.2
 - Moved from this document to D5.4
- ST5.3.3
 - Activities regarding MolDia have not been implemented as that project is not active.
 - CAPICE algorithm used as a functionally-equivalent replacement for GAVIN

10. Appendices

Appendix 1 - FAIR Maturity Assessment

DRA was assessed according to the Research Data Alliance (RDA) FAIR Data Maturity Model [21].

The results of the assessment form are shown below in Figures 11 and 12. It should be noted that the majority of the indicators are green and that the “radar plots”are generally good. However, the absence of certain key indicators prevents passing all of the FAIR indicators. This is largely down to the uncertainty of the post-CINECA environment around a) preservation of the data (e.g. RDA-A2-01M) and b) licensing of the data (RDA-R1.1-01M...03M) as these would need to be resolved outside of the CINECA project itself. Future work should be able to resolve these issues resulting in a fully-FAIR-compliant system.

Figure 11 - FAIR Maturity Summary

ID	PRINCIPLE	INDICATOR_ID	INDICATORS	PRIORITY	METRIC	VIZ	%
1	F	F1	RDA-F1-01M Metadata is identified by a persistent identifier	Essential	4 – fully implemented	4	1
2		F1	RDA-F1-01D Data is identified by a persistent identifier	Essential	4 – fully implemented	4	1
3		F1	RDA-F1-02M Metadata is identified by a globally unique identifier	Essential	4 – fully implemented	4	1
4		F1	RDA-F1-02D Data is identified by a globally unique identifier	Essential	4 – fully implemented	4	1
5		F2	RDA-F2-01M Rich metadata is provided to allow discovery	Essential	4 – fully implemented	4	1
6		F3	RDA-F3-01M Metadata includes the identifier for the data	Essential	4 – fully implemented	4	1
7		F4	RDA-F4-01M Metadata is offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed	Essential	4 – fully implemented	4	1
8	A	A1	RDA-A1-01M Metadata contains information to enable the user to get access to the data	Important	4 – fully implemented	4	1
9		A1	RDA-A1-02M Metadata can be accessed manually (i.e. with human intervention)	Essential	4 – fully implemented	4	1
10		A1	RDA-A1-02D Data can be accessed manually (i.e. with human intervention)	Essential	4 – fully implemented	4	1
11		A1	RDA-A1-03M Metadata identifier resolves to a metadata record	Essential	4 – fully implemented	4	1
12		A1	RDA-A1-03D Data identifier resolves to a digital object	Essential	4 – fully implemented	4	1
13		A1	RDA-A1-04M Metadata is accessed through standardised protocol	Essential	4 – fully implemented	4	1
14		A1	RDA-A1-04D Data is accessible through standardised protocol	Essential	4 – fully implemented	4	1
15		A1	RDA-A1-05D Data can be accessed automatically (i.e. by a computer program)	Important	4 – fully implemented	4	1
16		A1.1	RDA-A1.1-01M Metadata is accessible through a free access protocol	Essential	4 – fully implemented	4	1
17		A1.1	RDA-A1.1-01D Data is accessible through a free access protocol	Important	4 – fully implemented	4	1
18		A1.2	RDA-A1.2-01D Data is accessible through an access protocol that supports authentication and authorization	Useful	4 – fully implemented	4	1
19		A2	RDA-A2-01M Metadata is guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available	Essential	1 – not being considered this yet	1	0
20		I	I1	RDA-I1-01M Metadata uses knowledge representation expressed in standardised format	Important	4 – fully implemented	4
21	I1		RDA-I1-01D Data uses knowledge representation expressed in standardised format	Important	4 – fully implemented	4	1
22	I1		RDA-I1-02M Metadata uses machine-understandable knowledge representation	Important	4 – fully implemented	4	1
23	I1		RDA-I1-02D Data uses machine-understandable knowledge representation	Important	4 – fully implemented	4	1
24	I2		RDA-I2-01M Metadata uses FAIR-compliant vocabularies	Important	4 – fully implemented	4	1
25	I2		RDA-I2-01D Data uses FAIR-compliant vocabularies	Useful	4 – fully implemented	4	1
26	I3		RDA-I3-01M Metadata includes references to other metadata	Important	4 – fully implemented	4	1
27	I3		RDA-I3-01D Data includes references to other data	Useful	4 – fully implemented	4	1
28	I3		RDA-I3-02M Metadata includes references to other data	Useful	4 – fully implemented	4	1
29	I3		RDA-I3-02D Data includes qualified references to other data	Useful	3 – in implementation phase	3	0
30	I3	RDA-I3-03M Metadata includes qualified references to other metadata	Important	3 – in implementation phase	3	0	
31	I3	RDA-I3-04M Metadata include qualified references to other data	Useful	3 – in implementation phase	3	0	
32	R	R1	RDA-R1-01M Plurality of accurate and relevant attributes are provided to allow reuse	Essential	4 – fully implemented	4	1
33		R1.1	RDA-R1.1-01M Metadata includes information about the licence under which the data can be reused	Essential	3 – in implementation phase	3	0
34		R1.1	RDA-R1.1-02M Metadata refers to a standard reuse licence	Important	3 – in implementation phase	3	0
35		R1.1	RDA-R1.1-03M Metadata refers to a machine-understandable reuse licence	Important	3 – in implementation phase	3	0
36		R1.2	RDA-R1.2-01M Metadata includes provenance information according to community-specific standards	Important	4 – fully implemented	4	1
37		R1.2	RDA-R1.2-02M Metadata includes provenance information according to a cross-community language	Useful	4 – fully implemented	4	1
38		R1.3	RDA-R1.3-01M Metadata complies with a community standard	Essential	4 – fully implemented	4	1
39		R1.3	RDA-R1.3-01D Data complies with a community standard	Essential	4 – fully implemented	4	1
40	R1.3	RDA-R1.3-02M Metadata is expressed in compliance with a machine-understandable community standard	Essential	4 – fully implemented	4	1	
41	R1.3	RDA-R1.3-02D Data is expressed in compliance with a machine-understandable community standard	Important	4 – fully implemented	4	1	

Figure 12 - FAIR Maturity Scores

Appendix 2 - ST5.3.3 Example Report

Figure 13 shows an example report.

CINECA Pathology Report

Patient Information

Patient ID	Sample Date	Report Generated On
P199	2023-03-21	2023-04-12 09:52:18

Variant Associated Diseases (DisGenNet, Curated)

POSITION	VARIANT	GENE	DISEASE	CLASS
4:169477323-169477323	rs34324114	NEK1	Motor Neuron Disease	Nervous System Diseases

Other Variants (No curated Disease Associated)

POSITION	VARIANT	GENE	DISEASE	CLASS
1:976215-976215	rs7417106	PERM1	NA	NA
1:979034-979034	rs536503119	PERM1	NA	NA
1:52904685-52904685	rs72670819	ECHDC2	NA	NA
1:74205390-74205390	rs55882158	FPGT	NA	NA
1:88983825-88983825	NA	RBMXL1	NA	NA
1:89054646-89054646	NA	GBP1	NA	NA
1:226735804-226735804	rs708776	ITPKB	NA	NA
1:248441258-248441258	NA	OR2T7	NA	NA
2:88110465-88110465	rs72845818	SMYD1	NA	NA

Figure 13 - Example DRA report